

1 **Unlocking the high-rate continuous performance of fermentative hydrogen bioproduction**
2 **from fruit and vegetable residues by modulating hydraulic retention time**

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24 **Abstract**

25 Harnessing fruit-vegetable waste (FVW) as a resource to produce hydrogen via dark
26 fermentation (DF) embraces the circular economy concept. However, there is still a need to
27 upgrade continuous FVW-DF bioprocessing to enhance hydrogen production rates (HPR). This
28 study aims to investigate the influence of the hydraulic retention time (HRT) on the DF of FVW
29 by mixed culture. A stirred tank reactor under continuous mesophilic conditions was operated for
30 47 days with HRT stepwise reductions from 24 to 6 h, leading to organic loading rates between
31 47 and 188 g volatile solids (VS)/L-d. The optimum HRT of 9 h resulted in an unprecedented
32 HPR from FVW of 11.8 NL/L-d, with a hydrogen yield of 95.6 NmL/g VS fed. Based on an
33 overarching inspection of hydrogen production in conjunction with organic acids and
34 carbohydrates analyses, it was hypothesized that the high FVW-to-biohydrogen conversion rate
35 achieved was powered by lactate metabolism.

36

37 **Keywords:** Biohydrogen; Biorefinery; Dark fermentation; Fruit-vegetable waste; Process
38 optimization.

39 **1. Introduction**

40 To date, hydrogen holds a tremendous potential to mitigate the negative impact resulting from
41 the massive use of fossil-derived fuels not only owing to its elevated energy density (142 MJ/kg),
42 which is roughly 3-fold higher than that of methane, natural gas or gasoline, but also because
43 only water vapor is released during hydrogen combustion (Pathy et al., 2022). Unfortunately, a
44 huge amount of the hydrogen produced nowadays (approximately 60 million tonnes per year) is
45 derived directly or indirectly from fossil fuels (Muradov, 2017). A growing interest in the
46 generation of biogenic hydrogen has arisen over the last years. Biohydrogen is defined as the
47 hydrogen produced from biotechnologies such as bioelectrochemical systems, biophotolysis,
48 dark fermentation (DF), and photofermentation (Kim and Kim, 2011). Amongst them, DF is
49 nowadays regarded as one of the most promising biological routes for valorizing biomass into
50 hydrogen, owing to its mild culture conditions, relatively low operation costs, easy control, and
51 relatively high achievable hydrogen production rates (HPR) and yields (HY) (Luo et al., 2022;
52 Tran and Nguyen, 2022). Indeed, DF is a bioconversion process able to transform multiple
53 biodegradable wastes into hydrogen and organic acids, thus supporting the circular economy
54 concepts of “waste-to-energy” and “waste-to-commodity chemicals” (Mohan et al., 2016;
55 Boshagh, 2021).

56 Fruit & vegetable wastes (FVW) can be a sustainable feedstock for DF according to its
57 physicochemical characteristics such as high moisture (80-90%) and carbohydrates (70-90%)
58 contents, and the inherent presence of other macro/micronutrients needed for microbial growth
59 (Kaur et al., 2019). The latest statistical report stated that around 1.3 billion tonnes of food are
60 wasted per year, of which FVW represents approximately 42% (Ganesh et al., 2022). It is
61 estimated that, in the European Union, almost 22 kg of FVW are yearly generated per capita in

62 households (De Laurentiis et al., 2018). Processing industries, marketplaces and households are
63 the main identified sources of FVW. It should be highlighted that the management and disposal
64 of food waste (FW; including FVW) is a severe problem worldwide. In this context, the DF of
65 FVW is an ongoing endeavor to divert it from landfilling, open field dumping and incineration.
66 These traditional end-of-life options for FW not only causes pernicious greenhouse gas
67 emissions, unpleasant odors or leachates, but also promote a tremendous loss in circularity and
68 economic value (Basak et al., 2018; Magama et al., 2022).

69 Recent works have been focused on FVW valorization through hydrogen production by
70 DF (Gomez-Romero et al., 2014; Keskin et al., 2018; Gómez Camacho et al., 2019; Soltan et al.,
71 2019; Cieciora-Włoch et al., 2020; Dwivedi et al., 2020; Martínez-Mendoza et al., 2022). For
72 instance, Martínez-Mendoza et al. (2022) studied the influence of key operational parameters,
73 i.e., initial biomass concentration, pH, and initial total solids (TS) content, on the batch hydrogen
74 production of FVW via lactate-driven DF. That study achieved an unprecedented maximum
75 volumetric HPR of 23.4 NL/L-d at pH 7.0, 5% TS and 1.8 g volatile suspended solids (VSS)
76 biomass concentration. However, the number of studies on the continuous hydrogen production
77 from FVW is very limited. The highest HPR so far reported from FVW is only 1.4 ± 0.4 NL
78 $H_2/L-d$ (Gómez Camacho et al., 2019). Thus, engineering an efficient hydrogenogenic fermenter
79 under continuous mode is imperative for the scale-up and widespread implementation of DF
80 (Park et al., 2015). Some operational strategies used to improve the hydrogen production
81 efficiency include reactor design, bioaugmentation, additives supply, biomass and inoculum pre-
82 treatment, and control of environmental and operational process parameters such as hydraulic
83 retention time (HRT), organic loading rate (OLR), pH, and temperature (Sivagurunathan et al.,
84 2016; García-Depraect et al., 2023). Among them, the HRT, which represents the average time

85 that substrate remains in the reactor, is central for maximizing the HPR (Park et al., 2015;
86 Magama et al., 2022). It is accepted that higher waste-to-hydrogen bioconversion rates can be
87 achieved at low HRTs, albeit a too low HRT can lead to biomass washout and further process
88 collapse (Magama et al., 2022). Despite the relevance of the HRT on hydrogen production, there
89 is a lack of studies that modulate it to maximize the rate of FVW-to-hydrogen bioconversion.
90 Hence, this work aimed at evaluating the impact of HRT on the fermentative hydrogen
91 production from FVW. Soluble and non-soluble (by)products were considered in the assessment
92 of the process performance. A comprehensive energy and mass balance analysis of the process is
93 also presented with the purpose of assessing the baseline for a future design, analysis and
94 optimization of the DF of FVW in the next generation of biorefineries.

95

96 **2. Material and methods**

97 *2.1 Inoculum*

98 A hydrogenogenic mixed culture previously used in mesophilic batch fermentations producing
99 hydrogen from FVW via lactate-driven DF was employed as inoculum (Martínez-Mendoza et al.,
100 2022). Inoculum preparation involved the cultivation of an inoculum aliquot of 0.1 L (preserved
101 at 4 °C) for 19 h at 37 ± 1 °C and ~150 rpm, without pH control, in a 2.1-L gas-tight fermenter
102 with 0.9 L of mineral growth medium composed of (g/L): $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.15, $\text{FeCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 0.035,
103 KH_2PO_4 0.6, K_2HPO_4 2.4, lactose 10.0, $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ 2.5, and NH_4Cl 2.4. The resulting fresh and
104 active hydrogenogenic culture with a concentration of VSS of 180 mg/L was employed as
105 inoculum.

106 *2.2 Substrate*

107 Simulated FVW mimicking fruits and vegetables derived from a local marketplace was used as
108 the substrate. The substrate composition was prepared as reported in our previous study
109 (Martínez-Mendoza et al., 2022). The FVW was blended without tap water addition using a
110 semi-industrial blender (Sammic, XM-32, Spain) and frozen at -20 °C for storage. The
111 physicochemical characteristics of the blended FVW were as follows: pH 4.5 ± 0.1 , 111.3 ± 2.9
112 g total chemical oxygen demand (COD)/L, 96.7 ± 1.0 g soluble COD/L, 3.1 ± 0.1 g total
113 Kjeldahl nitrogen/L, 3.7 g phosphorus/L, 106.2 ± 0.5 g TS/L, 99.9 ± 0.5 g VS/L; total
114 carbohydrates $82.8 \pm 3.0\%$ w/w, protein $19.1 \pm 0.6\%$ w/w, lipids 1.2% w/w, and ash $5.9 \pm 0.6\%$
115 w/w (on a dry weight basis). The elemental composition was as follows: carbon $44.2 \pm 0.4\%$,
116 hydrogen $5.7 \pm 0.2\%$, oxygen $41.7 \pm 0.3\%$, and nitrogen $1.4 \pm 0.0\%$. Prior to feeding, FVW was
117 diluted using tap water to a final TS content of 5% (Martínez-Mendoza et al., 2022).

118

119 *2.3 Experimental set-up and process operation*

120 The continuous DF of FVW was evaluated using a polyvinyl chloride fermenter with a total
121 volume of 1.25 L (0.55 L head space) and equipped with a pH control device (BSV, Spain), a pH
122 probe (HO35-BSV01, Spain), gas & liquid sampling ports, and a continuous gas-flow meter
123 (Fig. 1). The fermenter was continuously operated for 47 days, divided in five operational stages
124 (I–V), at decreasing HRT values. The HRT was shortened from 24 to 16, 12, 9 and 6 h by rising
125 the feed flow rate at a constant concentration of 47.0 g VS/L (5% TS). Hence, the OLR
126 progressively increased from 47.0 to 70.6, 94.1, 125.4, and 188.1 g VS/L-d. The operational
127 parameters of the hydrogenogenic fermenter are summarized in Table 1. The hydrogenogenic
128 fermenter was placed at 37 ± 1 °C in a controlled-temperature room, magnetically stirred at ~
129 300 rpm, and maintained at pH 7.0 ± 0.1 (using NaOH 6 M). The hydrogenogenic fermenter was

130 seeded with 10% v/v of a recently collected hydrogenogenic microbial seed and operated in batch
131 mode for 8.5 h prior to continuous operation. Samples of 50 mL were periodically taken from the
132 influent and effluent in order to monitor the acidification degree, the organic acids profile, and
133 the removal efficiency of total carbohydrates. In addition, the flow rate and composition of the
134 acidogenic off-gas generated during the DF process was daily measured and reported as normal
135 volumes (NmL or NL) at standard pressure and temperature conditions (0 °C and 1 atm). The
136 main performance indicators of the procedure included the HPR and HY, the concentration of
137 hydrogen in the acidogenic off-gas, the hydrogen production stability index (HPSI), and the
138 energy production rate and yield (EPR and EY, respectively).

139

140 *2.4 Analytical procedures and data analysis*

141 Total carbohydrates, protein, pH, biogas composition, organic acids, COD, and solids were
142 determined as reported by Martínez-Mendoza et al. (2022). The HPSI was calculated as reported
143 by García-Depraect et al. (2020) using Eq. (1). The HPSI calculation considers variations in HPR
144 during each operational stage (not including HPR values from the first 3 HRTs in each
145 operational stage). A stability index equals to 1 means a constant HPR, while a deviation value in
146 HPR as large as the average HPR represents a stability index equals to 0. Thus, the higher the
147 HPSI index, the lower the dispersion of hydrogen production.

$$148 \quad HPSI = 1 - \frac{\text{Standard deviation HPR}}{\text{Average HPR}} \quad (1)$$

149 The degree of acidification was calculated as the ratio (in percentage) of the sum
150 concentration of organic acids (in COD equivalent) and the total COD of the influent (Martínez-
151 Mendoza et al., 2022). Whereas the mass balance analysis of COD was presented considering as
152 input the total COD of the influent, and for the output the COD equivalent of hydrogen (8 g

153 COD/g H₂) and organic acids produced, biomass growth, and residual carbohydrates (assuming
 154 glucose as the sugar). The biomass growth COD equivalent was estimated as 10% of the influent
 155 total COD (Chernicharo, 2007). The acetic acid that may be produced from homoacetogenesis
 156 ($HAC_{Homoacetogenesis}$) was determined using Eq. (2), as previously described by Montiel Corona
 157 and Razo-Flores (2018), where the concentration of organic acids and hydrogen gas are
 158 expressed in mmol.

$$159 \quad HAC_{Homoacetogenesis} = (2 \times [Butyric\ acid] + 2 \times [Acetic\ acid] - [Propionic\ acid] - \\ 160 \quad [H_2])/6 \quad (2)$$

161 Finally, the energy analysis was estimated in terms of EPR (kJ/L-d) and EY (kJ/g VS),
 162 calculated using Eq. (3), (4), respectively, where HPR is expressed in NL H₂/L-d, HV_{H_2} is the
 163 hydrogen heating value (286 kJ/mol), and HY stands for the hydrogen yield (NL H₂/g VS fed)
 164 (Kumar et al., 2016).

$$165 \quad EPR = \frac{Average\ HPR}{22.4} \times HV_{H_2} \quad (3)$$

$$166 \quad EY = \frac{Average\ HY}{22.4} \times HV_{H_2} \quad (4)$$

167

168 2.5. Statistical analysis

169 The experimental data analyzed were obtained under pseudo-steady state in each operational
 170 stage, except in stage V where no pseudo-steady state was achieved. When hydrogen
 171 productivities remained a minimum of 3 consecutive HRTs within $\pm 10\%$ variance, a pseudo-
 172 steady state was obtained. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using a Tukey test
 173 with a p-value < 0.05 to evaluate the impact of HRT on the process performance indicators.
 174 According to the Shapiro-Wilk test, data showed a normal distribution ($p \leq 0.05$). The software
 175 Statgraphics Centurion version 19.2.01 was used to perform the statistical analyses.

176 **3. Results and discussion**

177 *3.1. Influence of hydraulic retention time on hydrogen production performance*

178 The hydrogen production performance of a dark fermenter continuously fed with FVW at five
179 different HRTs (i.e., 24, 16, 12, 9, and 6 h) was evaluated for 47 days. Substrate concentration
180 was maintained at 47.0 g VS/L throughout the experiment, and therefore, the stepwise reduction
181 in HRT entailed a stepwise increase in the OLR (from 47.0 to 188.1 g VS/L-d; Table 1). The
182 OLR is the amount of substrate fed per unit volume of reactor per day, thus determining the
183 availability of substrate for hydrogen production. In the present study, the performance of FVW-
184 DF was assessed in regard to HRT for simplification purposes, but it is important to keep in mind
185 that the combined effect of HRT and OLR may impact the process performance of DF
186 (Sivagurunathan et al., 2016). The biogas production rate ranged from 6.0 to 19.7 NL/L-d
187 depending on the HRT assessed, while the hydrogen content in the gaseous phase remained
188 between 52.6 and 65.1% v/v. The HRT therefore exerted a severe impact on hydrogen production
189 efficiency (Fig. 2, Table 2). Particularly, process operation at an HRT of 24 and 16 h supported
190 similar HPR, HY, and hydrogen content values in the gas phase under pseudo-steady state (p-
191 value < 0.05), which accounted for 3.1 ± 0.2 NL H₂/L-d, 66.6 ± 4.0 NmL H₂/g VS fed and $52.6 \pm$
192 2.8% H₂ v/v, respectively. HPSI indices of 0.94 and 0.86 were obtained in stages I and II,
193 respectively, indicating a high hydrogen production stability. An HRT of 12 h in stage III
194 sustained an increase of 92 and 46% in HPR and HY, respectively, compared to process
195 operation at 16 and 24 h HRT. The HPSI recorded at 12 h HRT was 0.87. Likewise, the HPR and
196 HY ramped up to 11.8 ± 0.9 NL H₂/L-d and 95.6 ± 5.1 NmL H₂/g VS fed, respectively, during
197 stage IV (9 h HRT), which were 57 and 20% higher than those achieved in the previous
198 operational stage. At 9 h HRT and 125.4 g VS/L-d of OLR, the hydrogen content was 59.8% and

199 the HPSI reached a value of 0.91, which were statistically higher than those achieved in all the
200 previous stages. However, a further decrease in HRT from 9 to 6 h mediated a decrease of the
201 HPR by 40% and of HY by 60%, compared to those attained at an HRT of 9 h. This sharp
202 decrease in hydrogen production caused the collapse of the process and might be attributed to
203 organic overloading with an OLR of 188.1 g VS/L-d or biomass washout, as previously observed
204 elsewhere (Chen et al., 2012; Goud et al., 2014; Jung et al., 2022). Biomass washout has been
205 successfully prevented by the use of immobilized systems like the dynamic membrane reactor, in
206 which a self-forming biofilm layer is formed, during the filtration of the fermentation broth, on a
207 low-cost porous support such a stainless screen mesh via the deposition of bacteria and their
208 metabolites (Jung et al., 2022). Note that the hydrogen content in this last stage V was slightly
209 higher than those observed in the previous stages (on average 65.1%; Figure 2 and Table 2). It
210 has been indeed reported that the content of hydrogen in the gas produced is not a reliable
211 indicator of the process performance (Martínez-Mendoza et al., 2022; García-Depraect et al.,
212 2023). The temporary high hydrogen content observed before process collapse might be
213 attributed to the active addition of NaOH to control the pH when increasing the OLR, which can
214 modify the equilibrium of the $\text{CO}_2/\text{HCO}_3^-/\text{CO}_3^{2-}$ buffer system and impact on the composition of
215 the acidogenic off-gas.

216 Although it is difficult to make a fair comparison of data reported on the performance of
217 DF systems as it depends on the particular conditions of a given process, it is necessary to
218 benchmark the fermentative hydrogen production from complex feedstocks, FVW in this case.
219 The baseline for benchmarking herein used were the HY and HPR already reported in the
220 literature for similar FVW feedstocks. In batch experiments, the maximum HPR is estimated as
221 the highest hydrogen production rate (usually acquired from the modified Gompertz model)

222 divided by the working volume. Gomez-Romero et al. (2014) reported a maximum HPR of 5.6
223 NL H₂/L-d in the batch DF of FVW at pH of 5.5 and 37 °C. Later, Keskin et al. (2018)
224 conducted batch DF tests at 55 °C, initial pH of 7.0 and using a mix of FVW as substrate. The
225 authors reported maximum HPR and HY values ranging from 0.05 to 0.6 NL H₂/L-d and from 31
226 to 76 NmL H₂/g VS fed, respectively. Other study performing the batch DF (35 °C and pH 6.0)
227 of a mixture composed of 25% pea, 25% tomato, 25% banana and 25% orange reported a HY of
228 2.55 ± 0.07 NL H₂/L and a maximum HPR of 5.1 NL H₂/L-d (Soltan et al., 2019). Dwivedi et al.
229 (2020) investigated the effect of pH (5.5–8) and food-to-microorganism (F/M) ratio (0.5–2) on
230 the mesophilic (35–40 °C) hydrogen production from FVW. The authors found pH 7.5 and F/M
231 1:1 the best condition leading to the highest maximum volumetric HPR of 0.03 NL H₂/L-d. In
232 another study, Cieciora-Włoch et al. (2020) investigated the semi-continuous, mesophilic DF of
233 FVW and reported a HY of 52.1 NmL H₂/g VS at pH 5.5, an OLR of ≈ 15 g VS/L-d, and a solid
234 retention time of 72 h. Gómez Camacho et al. (2019) assessed the continuous DF of a mixture of
235 FVW under mesophilic conditions (35 °C) and reported the highest HPR and HY to be 1.4 ± 0.4
236 NL H₂/L-d and 74 ± 29 NmL H₂/g VS, respectively, at an HRT of 36 h and an OLR of 19.4 ± 5.6
237 g VS/L-d. More recently, Martínez-Mendoza et al. (2022) achieved a HY of 50 NmL H₂/g VS
238 fed with an outstanding maximum volumetric HPR of 23.4 NL H₂/L-d from the lactate-driven
239 DF of FVW conducted under batch mode at constant pH (7.0) and temperature (35 °C). Here it is
240 worth highlighting that there is a lack of studies evaluating the continuous DF of FVW. In this
241 regard, the HPR achieved in the present study is the highest so far reported, even using FVW
242 without nutrient supplementation and without applying pretreatment or hydrolysis procedures. In
243 comparison to other complex organic waste like FW, the HPR achieved herein with FVW is
244 comparatively higher than the highest hydrogen productivity (7.1 ± 0.4 NL H₂/L-d) so far

245 reported for the continuous DF of FW (Jung et al., 2022), likely due to the existing differences in
246 the physicochemical composition between substrates.

247 Carbohydrate removal efficiency ranged from $65.6 \pm 0.9\%$ to $79.2 \pm 0.8\%$ along the
248 experiment (Table 2). Interestingly, the efficiency of carbohydrate consumption was not
249 correlated either positively or negatively with that of hydrogen production. One possible
250 explanation for that is associated with substrate competition issues between non-hydrogen
251 producing bacteria and hydrogen producers. In this context, it is well known that HRT/OLR can
252 shape the microbial communities involved in the DF process. In general, it has been reported that
253 high HRT (low OLR) values may trigger the dominance of lactic acid bacteria (LAB) over
254 hydrogen-producing bacteria (HPB), thereby leading to poor hydrogen production efficiencies
255 (García-Depraect et al., 2021b; Palomo-Briones et al., 2021). In contrast, low HRTs (high OLR)
256 are often more conducive for the growth of HPB, thus maximizing hydrogen production (García-
257 Depraect et al., 2021a). Here the continuous hydrogen production from FVW was biocatalysed
258 by a mixed bacterial culture, which has the metabolic capacity of transforming carbohydrates
259 into lactate and of producing hydrogen from lactate (García-Depraect et al., 2022; Martínez-
260 Mendoza et al., 2022; Regueira-Marcos et al., 2023). Effective lactate cross-feeding between
261 LAB and some HPB (e.g., *Clostridium butyricum*) is keystone in metabolizing lactate as
262 hydrogen precursor (García-Depraect et al., 2021b). Indeed, lactate was one of the major
263 metabolites detected in the fermentation broth (effluent) throughout the operation (as will be
264 discussed in section 3.2). Thus, it is highly probable that the high FVW-to-hydrogen
265 bioconversion rates herein achieved were powered by beneficial associations between LAB and
266 HPB, which were apparently boosted at 9 h HRT and impaired at either higher or lower HRTs.
267 Further microbiology approaches can shed light on this inference (Kumar et al., 2018).

268 3.2 Effect of hydraulic retention time on the profile of organic acids

269 The main soluble metabolites identified for all the operational stages in the effluent were lactate,
270 formate, acetate, propionate, and iso-valerate, whereas ethanol was not detected (Fig. 3). For 24
271 h of HRT, an accumulation of lactate of 10.5 ± 1.2 g/L was obtained as the main metabolite in
272 this operational stage, followed by acetate, butyrate, iso-valerate, formate and propionate (with
273 concentrations of 6.7 ± 2.3 , 4.7 ± 2.1 , 4.6 ± 0.3 , 1.3 ± 0.4 , and 0.4 ± 0.3 g/L, respectively). The
274 highest and lowest lactate concentration in the effluent was 18.4 ± 1.2 g/L and 13.3 ± 0.9 g/L,
275 observed at 16 and 6 h of HRT, respectively. The higher OLR at the shortest HRT of 6 h did not
276 entail neither an enhanced lactate accumulation, nor higher HY and HPR. A marked lactate
277 accumulation in the fermentation broth has been typically associated with hydrogen inhibition
278 (García-Depraect et al., 2021b; Palomo-Briones et al., 2021). However, in this study, efficient
279 hydrogen production was achieved despite lactate accumulation (stage V). As mentioned before,
280 one explanation for that is that the inoculum used, which has been previously proven to support
281 the lactate-driven DF of FVW, was able to metabolize lactate into hydrogen. Indeed, this is the
282 first study that use a hydrogenogenic inoculum able to perform lactate-driven DF to produce
283 continuously hydrogen from FVW. Also, during all the operational stages, the concentration of
284 acetate, iso-valerate, and propionate decreased with lower HRT by 58, 85, and 50%,
285 respectively. Formate concentration increased simultaneously from 1.3 ± 0.4 g/L until 3.3 ± 0.9
286 g/L when hydrogen production sharply dropped at 6 h of HRT. Interestingly, butyrate
287 concentration was virtually constant during the operational stages involving hydrogen production
288 (I–IV), showing a decrease of 38% during the last operational stage when organic overload or
289 biomass washout could have strongly impaired the hydrogen production. In general, the decrease
290 in HRT led to a marked reduction in the recovery of carboxylic acids, resulting in acidification

291 degrees of $62.4 \pm 1.0\%$, $56.4 \pm 3.6\%$, $53.2 \pm 1.5\%$, $46.9 \pm 3.7\%$, and $42.9 \pm 3.0\%$ at 24, 16, 12, 9
292 and 6 h of HRT, respectively (Table 3).

293 Organic acids, hydrogen gas, residual sugars, and biomass were included in the COD
294 mass balance with a recovery range of 94.2–83.7% (Table 3), which means that most of
295 metabolites produced during the fermentation were quantified. The small loss of COD can be
296 explained by the presence of other compounds in the FVW used that were not measured or
297 remained unoxidized. According to the COD balance, hydrogen recovery accounted for 3.9–
298 6.1% of the total COD present in the substrate. The highest hydrogen recovery obtained at high
299 OLR of 125.4 g VS/L-d could be explained by the fact that high substrate availability can boost
300 electron flux to divert to hydrogen production (Wu et al., 2012). High substrate availability can
301 also favor the growth of HPB over homoacetogens such as *Acetobacterium woodii* and *Blautia*
302 *coccoides*. In this study, the share of acetate that may be produced via homoacetogenesis
303 decreased (from 31.1 ± 3.0 to $4.8 \pm 5.0\%$) with HRT shortening (high OLR), which agrees well
304 with previous observations (Fuentes et al., 2021). However, it went up to $14.1 \pm 5.8\%$ when
305 hydrogen production was impaired at 6 h HRT (Table 3). It should be noted that this way of
306 estimating homoacetogenesis assumes the production of hydrogen via butyric- and acetic-
307 pathways, as well as propioneogenesis and homoacetogenesis as hydrogen sink pathways. Thus,
308 hydrogen production from lactate, which can use acetate as electron acceptor (García-Depraect et
309 al., 2021a), is overlooked in Eq. (2). Overall, in the present study, the observed profile of organic
310 acids suggests that lactate-driven DF was key in achieving high hydrogen production
311 performance using FVW as substrate.

312

313 *3.3 Energy and mass balance analysis*

314 Based on the HPR and HY achieved, the average EPR and EY ranged from 40.0 to 150.3 kJ/L-d
315 and from 0.5 to 1.2 ± 0.1 kJ/g VS fed, respectively (Table 4). A similar EY of 1.5 kJ/g VS was
316 reported from the DF of FW (Ghimire et al., 2015). An energy and mass balance analysis of the
317 process was performed based on a daily feed of 1000 kg of FVW (99.9 kg VS) and considering
318 the operational conditions of operational stage IV (HRT of 9 h and OLR of 125.4 g VS/L-d),
319 which led to the highest HPR and HY. As shown in Fig. 4, 1000 kg of FVW per day would be
320 managed by a working volume of reactor of ≈ 0.8 m³ and produce up to 9.4 m³ H₂ per day with
321 an associated HY of 94.1 L H₂/kg VS fed or 9.4 L H₂/kg FVW. In other words, 1255 kg of FVW
322 would be managed by 1 m³ working volume. Such a hydrogen production would produce 120
323 MJ per day, implying an EPR of 150.3 MJ/m³-d and an EY of 1.2 MJ/kg VS fed or 0.1 MJ/kg
324 FVW. Regarding the soluble by-products, the resulting fermentation broth would contain 13.2,
325 4.1, 3.2, 2.3, 1.1, and 0.2 kg/m³ of lactate, butyrate, acetate, formate, iso-valerate and propionate,
326 respectively. Such building blocks can be further used together with the remaining sugars as
327 carbon and energy source for other biotechnologies, for instance, anaerobic digestion that does
328 not require a downstream step for the recovery and purification of organic acids (Montiel
329 Corona and Razo-Flores, 2018; García-Depraect et al., 2020).

330 Although an outstanding HPR was achieved herein, further endeavours are still needed to
331 improve the DF of FVW. Some technical issues, such as process instability and insufficient HPR
332 and HY, must be overcome before process scale-up. Future work should deeply investigate the
333 microbiology of the process and explore promising enhancement strategies such as the use of
334 conductive materials such as magnetite, which has been reported to promote the bioconversion of
335 lactate into hydrogen (Kim et al., 2022).

336 **4. Conclusions**

337 The effect of HRT on continuous FVW-DF was investigated. The HRT exerted a markedly
338 impact on HPR/HY. Low process performance was observed at HRTs above 12 h, while 6 h
339 HRT resulted in process collapse due to organic overloading or biomass washout. The highest
340 HPR (11.8 NL/L-d) and HY (95.6 NmL/g VS fed) were recorded at 9 h HRT. The major by-
341 products were lactate, acetate and butyrate throughout the operation while hydrogen production
342 did not correlate with carbohydrates consumption, which together suggested the occurrence of
343 lactate-driven hydrogen-producing pathway(s). Overall, FVW is a good feedstock for hydrogen
344 production, producing 150.3 kJ/L-d.

345

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499 **Figure captions:**

500 **Figure 1.** Photograph (a) and scheme (b) of the continuous dark fermentation set-up used to
501 investigate the effect of hydraulic retention time on the FVW-to-hydrogen biotransformation.
502 Peristaltic pump (1 and 11), magnetic stirrer (2), dark fermenter (3), gas outlet (4), gas sampling
503 port (5), water column (6), gas counter (7), pH probe (8), pH controller (9), 6 N NaOH solution
504 (10).

505

506 **Figure 2.** Time course of a) hydraulic retention time (HRT) and organic loading rate (OLR); b)
507 biogas production rate (BPR) and hydrogen content in the acidogenic off-gas, and c)
508 hydrogen production rate (HPR) and yield (HY), recorded during the continuous dark
509 fermentation of fruit-vegetable waste.

510

511 **Figure 3.** Box and whisker plot of the concentration of organic acids recorded at pseudo-steady
512 state at different operational stages. IQR: Interquartile range. No pseudo-steady state was
513 achieved in operational stage V.

514

515 **Figure 4.** Energy recovery and mass balance of the continuous dark fermentation of fruit-
516 vegetable waste.

517 **Table 1.** Operational parameters of the continuous hydrogenogenic fermenter.

Parameter	Operational stage				
	I	II	III	IV	V
Time (days)	0-6.0	6.0-18.5	18.5-26.5	26.5-41.5	41.5-46.5
HRT (h)	24	16	12	9	6
OLR (g VS/L-d)	47.0	70.6	94.1	125.4	188.1
HRT cycles	5.9	18.0	16.0	39.7	22.4

518 **Note:** OLR: organic loading rate; HRT: hydraulic retention time; VS: volatile solids.

519 **Table 2.** Pseudo-steady state operational performance indicators for hydrogen production under
 520 different operational conditions using fruit-vegetable waste as substrate.

Parameter	Operational stage				
	I	II	III	IV	V
BPR (NL/L-d)	6.0 ± 0.6	6.9 ± 1.0	12.7 ± 1.7	19.7 ± 1.8	11.1 ± 4.4
HPR (NL H ₂ /L-d)	3.1 ± 0.2	3.9 ± 0.5	7.5 ± 1.0	11.8 ± 0.9	7.1 ± 2.7
HY (NmL H ₂ /g VS fed)	66.6 ± 4.0	54.6 ± 6.7	79.5 ± 10.3	95.6 ± 5.1	37.9 ± 14.1
Hydrogen content (% v/v)	52.6 ± 2.8	56.6 ± 2.4	59.0 ± 1.1	59.8 ± 1.6	65.1 ± 3.3
HPSI	0.94	0.86	0.87	0.91	0.63
Total carbohydrates removal (%)	79.2 ± 0.8	75.1 ± 0.7	74.1 ± 0.3	73.5 ± 0.3	65.6 ± 0.9

521 **Notes:** Mean value ± standard deviation. **BPR:** biogas production rate; **HPR:** hydrogen
 522 production rate; **HY:** hydrogen yield; **HPSI:** hydrogen production stability index. No pseudo-
 523 steady state was achieved in operational stage V. The number of samples analyzed was 8 (days
 524 3.5-5.5), 17 (days 11.9-18.0), 14 (days 18.5-25.9), 25 (days 30.9-40.9) and 13 (days 42.5-46.5)
 525 for the operational stage I, II, II, IV, and V, respectively.

526 **Table 3.** Acidification degree, homoacetogenesis degree, and COD mass balance analysis for the
 527 different conditions tested.

Parameter	Operational stage				
	I	II	III	IV	V
Acidification degree (%)	60.3 ± 4.3	56.4 ± 3.6	53.2 ± 1.5	46.9 ± 3.7	42.9 ± 3.0
^a HAc _{Homoacetogenesis} (%)	31.1 ± 3.0	13.5 ± 1.4	8.2 ± 2.5	4.8 ± 5.0	14.1 ± 5.8
COD equiv. organic acids (g/L)	31.6 ± 2.2	29.5 ± 1.9	27.9 ± 0.8	24.6 ± 2.0	22.1 ± 1.4
COD equiv. hydrogen (g/L)	2.4 ± 0.5	2.0 ± 0.1	3.0 ± 0.0	3.2 ± 0.1	1.1 ± 0.5
COD equiv. residual sugars (g/L)	9.3 ± 0.3	11.2 ± 0.3	11.7 ± 0.1	11.9 ± 0.1	15.5 ± 0.4
^b COD Recovery (%)	92.8 ± 2.9	91.6 ± 1.9	91.1 ± 1.5	85.7 ± 3.7	83.7 ± 1.9

528 **Notes:** Mean value ± standard deviation. ^a HAc_{Homoacetogenesis}: putative acetic acid derived from
 529 homoacetogenesis; ^b It was assumed that 10% of the total COD concentration of substrate was
 530 diverted to biomass growth (Chernicharo, 2007). COD: chemical oxygen demand. No pseudo-
 531 steady state was achieved in operational stage V. The number of samples analyzed was 4, 7, 3, 5
 532 and 4 for the operational stage I, II, II, IV, and V, respectively.

533 **Table 4.** Energy production analysis at pseudo-steady state under different operational
 534 conditions for the dark fermentation of fruit-vegetable waste.

Parameter	Operational stage				
	I	II	III	IV	V
EPR (kJ/L-d)	40.0 ± 2.4	49.7 ± 6.8	95.5 ± 12.4	150.3 ± 12.0	90.9 ± 34.0
EY (kJ/g VS fed)	0.9 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	1.0 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.2

535 **Note:** EPR: energy production rate; EY: energy yield. No pseudo-steady state was achieved in
 536 operational stage V. The number of samples analyzed was 8, 17,14, 25 and 13 for the operational
 537 stage I, II, II, IV, and V, respectively.

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Fig. 1

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Fig. 2

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Fig. 3

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Fig. 4